

Evidence-based, digitally-enabled support and care for older pre-frail adults

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Abstract. Frailty and cognitive decline co-occur in ageing populations, motivating scalable multidomain prevention. We present an mHealth app for pre-frail/frail older adults (≥ 55), part of the COMFORTage project, combining: progressive multicomponent exercise with visual guidance; protein-aware meal planning with nutrient feedback; a structured educational path with quizzes; and wearable-supported self-monitoring. In a qualitative think-aloud ($n=5$; 4 non-expert smartphone users, 1 highly confident), participants completed representative tasks across modules and reported the app as easy to use and helpful, with minor suggestions on recipe grouping/localization. The resulted prototype will be assessed under an 18-month randomized study.

Keywords. mHealth, frailty, older adults, exercise prescription, nutrition planning, health literacy, wearable monitoring

1. Introduction and background

Frailty is common in community-dwelling older adults and increases risk of disability and cognitive decline [1]. Multidomain lifestyle interventions can delay decline but require sustained engagement [2]. Evidence supports the feasibility of mHealth applications for frailty/pre-frailty self-management [3] and mobile interventions for dementia-risk reduction [4]. Yet, many approaches emphasize either frailty management or dementia prevention, and do not tightly integrate frailty-tailored exercise, protein-focused meal planning with nutrient feedback (learning-by-doing), and structured health-literacy reinforcement in a single intervention app. COMFORTage brings these elements together, complemented by wearable-enabled monitoring and secure data pipeline, and we report early qualitative usability findings to inform iterative refinement.

2. Methods and preliminary findings

The app provides: (1) Exercise—weekly multicomponent training (strength, balance, aerobic, flexibility) aligned with WHO guidance [5], delivered as progressive intensity

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levels with step-by-step multimedia instructions and completion tracking; (2) Nutrition—dietitian-seeded plans and a recipe catalogue emphasizing adequate protein, enabling daily meal planning with real-time calorie/macro feedback, consistent with ESPEN geriatrics guidance [6]; (3) Education—progressive modules on frailty, cardiovascular health, physical activity and nutrition with short quizzes and reinforcement messages; (4) Wearables support monitoring of activity, sleep and weight to complement self-reported adherence; (5) gamified rewards for boosting engagement.

Qualitative think-aloud usability testing was performed with 5 older adults (≥ 55) at Hippokrateion Hospital. Participants completed one task per module (education quiz; exercise completion; recipe selection, meal-plan creation and nutrient feedback review). Facilitators used neutral prompts and a structured observation form; participants provided verbal feedback on ease-of-use and helpfulness. Four participants reported smartphone experience but low confidence, while one reported high confidence. Overall feedback was positive across core flows; minor suggestions concerned recipe grouping/localization. Standardized usability scales will be included in later iterations.

Figure 1. Physical exercise and nutritional guidance as main intervention

3. Conclusions

COMFORTage integrates frailty-tailored exercise, nutrition learning-by-doing, and health-literacy support within a secure mHealth-and-wearables pipeline; early usability indicates feasibility ahead of n. Future work includes the evaluation of intervention in an 18-month single-center randomized controlled study including about 200 older adults.

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